

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN FOOTBALL TEACHING

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Abstract: *Effective ways of introducing new technologies in football teaching in order to increase the intensity of training are discussed.*

Key words: *Football, training, competitions, workouts, activities, recreation.*

Аннотация: *Обсуждаются эффективные пути внедрения новых технологий в преподавание футбола с целью повышения интенсивности тренировок.*

Ключевые слова: *Футбол, тренировки, соревнования, тренировки, мероприятия, отдых.*

Annotatsiya: *Mashg'ulotlar intensivligini oshirish maqsadida futbol o'qitishga yangi texnologiyalarni joriy etishning samarali usullari muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Futbol, mashg'ulotlar, musobaqalar, mashg'ulotlar, tadbirlar, dam olish.*

Promotion of physical culture and sports, the population, especially creating the necessary conditions and infrastructure to promote a healthy lifestyle among young people, the country's international sports Consistent measures are being taken to ensure a decent participation in the field.

Exercises that serve this process are sports in a strict sequence and sequence to the training sessions is started. The physical qualities of the players today from special tools for training, exercise, mobility and national requires the use of a set of games.

The training should be carried out systematically, according to the plan for a long time should not be stopped during. Only then can it be an important factor in improving the skills of the players. During the training, the players have a positive emotional state to bring them the purpose of the training and competitions, the results need to be explained. There are also different styles of training, use forms and tools, change conditions, training it is necessary to include elements of competition.

It is necessary to create favorable conditions for training and competitions. That's it however, it should be borne in mind that a player may encounter different

conditions many times during the tournament. Therefore, he must be able to adapt to these conditions, and this is achieved through special training.

During the training, the ability and skill of the players increased strictly pedagogical and physician throughout the entire session to attend it is necessary to establish control. The following is the purpose of the exercise

The main conditions of creation are:

1. Graduality in determining the norm of sports loads. Proper rotation of competition, training and rest.
2. Optimal rhythm of sports activities.
3. Systematization in the distribution of exercises, training and competitions and consistency
4. Sports workloads will be gradually increased by increasing the total workload, training intensity and duration.

In this case:

- A) Work slowly during each training session and competition to enter;
- B) rest, illness, injury and other interruptions in training (not training for a certain period of time) then gradually start working;
- C) sports in certain parts, stages, periods of annual cycles to increase and decrease the load gradually should.

Pre-workout and pre-competition writing exercises carried out. Its content is the status of the players and their varies depending on individual characteristics and environmental conditions.

There was a delay in their training and this delay was their work special training for players who have a negative impact on their ability mode is created, which depends on the level of preparation of the whole group continues until they reach Accelerate training rather, it is important to gradually enter training competitions.

Competitions in training cycles and inter-game cycles and from weekends to workouts, larger than the average workload the gradual transition to loaded workouts and vice versa to large loaded workouts is observed.

The cycle in which the loads are changed at two-day rest intervals, and then continues in the order approximately after the rest, is called the exercise cycle. Competition is also a training tool. Loads vary between two races, approximately each a cycle that is repeated in a post-race order is called an inter-game cycle.

Competitions are a benchmark for determining the level of sports load (target). It is known that they are in the body of the player differs from training in that it has a large impact. Heavy-duty workouts do not produce a reaction as clearly as they would

during a competition. Suffice it to say that after a moderate workout, players lose 1 kg, after a large workout - about 2 kg, and after the competition - 3 kg.

Approximately similar physiological changes can also be observed based on changes in pulse rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, dynamometry, electrical sensitivity of the eye, and other parameters.

It is very important to know the laws of recovery processes in the body of players after various sports loads. How recovery processes occur is studied on a number of criteria (blood pressure, electrocardiogram readings, weight, measurement of arm muscle strength, vascular tone, heart rate, electrical sensitivity of the eye: the effect on additional loads, etc.).

Training and competition players experience fatigue in the body causes to be; for complete recovery, especially if the body is not given enough rest to restore nerve cells, this can lead to fatigue without fatigue.

1. Rest is an integral part of training, during which the player's body is organized in such a way that after each training session and competition it maintains an increasing ability to work.

2. The following forms of rest are observed in the player's activity: Pause between exercises (micropauses). Daily rest (during the day, during breaks in games, in training, in sleep).

3. Weekly rest (at the end, at the beginning of each cycle).

4. Annual vacation.

The first condition of the purposeful training - is to adhere to optimal continuous rest intervals between workouts, workouts, and competitions. They last too long should not be (at the same time not too short). In the body while helping to ensure the success of the recovery process, the rest should not lose track of previous work, i.e., training outcomes.

The duration and content of the holiday was held earlier is determined by the intensity of the exercise, training or competition and the level of training of the player. With the increase in the level of exercise, the recovery process in the body passes faster, so it takes less time to recover, and rest intervals can be shorter.

The doctor with the coach conducts various exercises, competitions and games how the recovery processes go after cycles between learn and the optimal intervals of rest of the players determine.

These sports loads are high and competitions are frequent to prevent fatigue and to make better use of exercises, trainings and competitions to increase the performance of players in sports and to improve their skills.

The content of the holiday should be strictly individualized.

Particular attention is paid to the organization of weekly and annual vacations, as often such vacations take place in a passive form, which greatly reduces the ability of players to work.

Competitions are great for the body, primarily for the nervous system demands even higher than the workload. Therefore, post-race rest intervals, should be more than a post-workout rest.

Row it is necessary to rest after competitions. Recreation can be in a way that distracts athletes from high sports workload, depending on the conditions of the competition (reducing the intensity of training, switching to another type of training, additional rest, etc.).

In addition, the process of recovery in the body of players special recovery measures (bathing, massage, consumption of foods rich in vitamins) are carried out for its successful passage.

It is also important to pay attention to the players 'sleep and eating habits, personal hygiene and so on.

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